

THE EFFECT OF DIGITAL INDIA PROGRAM WITH REFERENCE TO CHENNAI CITY- AN CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The goal of the Digital India Program is to turn India into a knowledge economy that is digitally empowered. It is a government of India project that aims to bring together government departments and Indian citizens. Its goal is to ensure citizens have access to government services via electronic means while eliminating paper effort. This research aims to see how the Digital India Program affects people. This describes how the economy is changing in different industries. **Dipankar Saikia (2020)** Prime Minister Narendra Modi announced a significant program named "The Digital India Programme" on July 2nd, 2015, with the goal of India's transformation towards a knowledge economy and digitally connected society. In this light, this article focuses on the effectiveness of the Digital India Program in the context of Chennai. The research was carried out in the city of Chennai. The data for this study was obtained on working male and female populations using self-administered questionnaires. To satisfy the research objectives, the collected information was analyzed using statistical procedures such as percentage analysis, paired t-test, and reliability test via statistical software for mathematical reasoning. Finally, with a wide sample size in multiple locations, this study may yield even more results.

Keywords: Digital India Programme, Services, Various sectors, Awareness and Effectiveness of Digital Empowerment.

INTRODUCTION

Our Honorable Prime Minister of India launched Digital India in July 2015, with the goal of connecting rural areas to high-speed Internet and promoting digital literacy. Bharat net, digital locker, online-education, online-health, online-sign, online-shopping, and a national scholarship portal are some of the services that will be made available through this introduction. The initial purpose of Digital India is to come up with new and practical ideas. By leveraging digital innovations, the Prime Minister envisions modernizing our country and providing

possibilities to all residents. His vision is for every citizen to have access to digital services, knowledge, and information. In order to actualize Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam's vision of a digital India, this group will develop policies and best practices from all around the world.

Three essential features of digital India are the development of digital infrastructure, digital literacy, and digital service delivery across the country. Mr. Narendra Modi, the Prime Minister of India, has launched an initiative called India's digital transformation. The mission's purpose is to create a digital India and increase citizen participation, transparency, and responsiveness in governance. It aspires to provide all services electronically and foster digital literacy in India by leveraging digital technologies such as cloud computing and mobile apps, which have emerged as a driving force for express economic growth and citizen empowerment. As a result, businesses from all over the world are eager to contribute to the digital India objective.

Scope of the Digital India

- To prepare India for a knowledgeable future by building central technology that will enable revolution; this programme encompasses a wide range of departments under one umbrella.
- On being revolutionary and for realizing the IT (Indian Talent), IT (Information Technology), and IT (Information Security) this programme brings together a wide range of ideas and thoughts into a single, comprehensive vision, making the mission transformative in its entirety.
- Many existing initiatives will be refocused, reformed, and delivered in a synchronized manner for their transformative impact under the digital transformation program.

The goal of Digital India is to bring much-needed clarity to the nine growth pillars listed below.

- Highways with high-speed internet.
- Mobile Connectivity is available to everyone.
- The Internet Access Program for the Public.
- e-Government: Using Technology to Reform Government
- e-Kranti is an acronym for "Electronic Delivery of Services."
- Information for everyone.
- Electronics production.
- Job-related IT.

Research Objectives

- The purpose of this study is to assess the efficiency of the Digital India Program in Chennai.
- To determine which sectors/areas of digital India services are being used.
- To review digital India and the challenges in transforming it into digital.

- To explore the uses of the Digital India Programme.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Binod Kumar (2020) the development of the Indian economy has been supported by digitalization. The clearest model is the expansion in work possibilities for youngsters in the provincial region. Moreover to the prior, the "Make in India" drive has given youngsters an immense push to lay out new organizations and thought of creative ways of adding to India's digitization. On its part, the Indian government is compelling and empowering its residents to take out the requirement for cash decrease their reliance on exchanges including cash. The objective is to inspire us to acknowledge computerized instalments. Computerized exchanges compel us to seek after a lawful way that helps the economy. Since it depends on specialized standards, the use of plastic cash furnishes residents with both opportunity and security. The overall globe will profit from advanced instalments. Since cash is the key mode of exchange in psychological oppression funding and illegal tax avoidance, a robotized society approves to prevent comparing exercises. The inventory of high web is significant spine of computerized foundation. Digitization has brought about the successful conveyance of administrations to individuals of the country because of the improvement of updated and quicker portable web associations.

Dr. Pardeep Bawa Sharma (2020), promotion affects individuals' way of behaving, and it contrasts from one person to another because of shifting bits of knowledge and levels of understanding. Orientation, age bunch, geological region, capability, and foundation all impact a singular's insight. Openness to print, social, and regular media, then again, decides consciousness of any promotion.

Rajan Gupta (2020) shows that superior e-administration prompts more grounded majority rule government, which can be accomplished by expanding framework certainty, deceivability, and straightforwardness, which can all be won through fruitful marking. Various information investigation philosophies can assist with framework trust and straightforwardness. The review's motivation is to utilize examination to work on a few areas of marking, like correspondence, consistency, lucidity, and rivalry, to address numerous hardships in the public area. The exploration plan for this study incorporates both subjective and quantitative systems, like enlightening insights. A portion of the essential methodologies that have arisen for information examination incorporate rating and positioning investigation of government applications, virtual entertainment investigation, message and discourse examination, media examination, factual examination and information mining, telecom examination, and individuals socioeconomics for taxpayer supported initiatives. The "Advanced India" crusade under the e-administration drive was viewed as very fruitful in light of the many kinds of logical strategies found in the review.

Aly, H. (2020) Computerized reasoning (artificial intelligence) is changing the existences of many individuals in both creating and created nations as a feature of the Fourth Modern Transformation. Monstrous computerized developments are changing the economies of those nations, with them many expected benefits incorporates various new worries. The focal point

of this examination is to take a gander at the connection between monetary turn of events, work efficiency, and work on one hand, and overall, computerized change part Man-made brainpower (simulated intelligence) and the fourth insurgency improvements going as other.

Subhadeep Dutta (2020) saw that innovation has now contacted each part of presence, making digitalization a characteristic piece of our day to day routines. We can't get by without electronic gadgets in this day and age. Because of the send-off of the Computerized India project, mechanical progressions have expanded by an enormous improvement. Data correspondence innovation (ICT) has become progressively significant in this period of data innovation and data blast (ICT) is basic for the advancement of training and libraries, as well concerning further developing help quality. Kids and youngsters' play, admittance to data, correspondence, learning, re-learning, and un-learning have all been upset by the advanced transformation.

Carla Fernandes and et.al (2021) from January 2011 to September 2019, the commitment of advanced monetary administrations to monetary consideration in Mozambique was determined utilizing the Autoregressive Disseminated Slack (ARDL) model. The job of computerized monetary administrations in Mozambique's monetary consideration is examined utilizing two models (as characterized by the quantity of financial balances). In the main model, customary advanced instalment components like ATMs, retail location (POSs), electronic between and intra-bank cash moves, direct charge, and home-grown and cross-line settlements are incorporated as free variables. The second model considers state of the art computerized instalment techniques like web banking, versatile banking, and electronic cash. With the exception of home-grown settlements and direct charge, which have restricted commonness and derive that the leftover factors add to monetary consideration in the nation and by means of web banking exercises. Because of the discoveries, advanced monetary administrations are turning out to be more fundamental as far as monetary consideration, especially as far as further developing admittance to and utilization of administrations by poor people.

Shruti Jain (2020) by and large, women's activist gatherings have needed inclusivity, emerging from a restricted Western privileged brain research and focused on their own issues and requests. Another period of women's liberation has arisen because of the computerized upheaval. By encouraging inclusivity and supporting openness in organizing aggregate activity, the advanced circle can help women's activist extremist developments. It additionally supports the winding of neighbourhood and worldwide accounts to uncover normal primary awkward nature. At the same time, the computerized domain can likewise act as a rich ground for sexism and sexism. This is a speedy assessment of what digitalization means for ladies' developments, especially in arising economies like India. It achieves this by utilizing postcolonial and postmodern women's activist speculations to inspect contemporary digital woman's rights. The brief likewise examines the benefits and drawbacks of advanced activism.

Adrian Athique (2019) as per his examination paper, India's demonetization, which started in November 2016, over the next year, it will keep on spreading its foundations and effect. He likewise expressed that this intercession was arranged as a feature of a bigger overall money related try. The publication centers around overall news and assessment, impact gauges at

Indian scholastics, and India's administration expressed targets. Demonetization currently has a reasonable connection to the worldwide "credit only plan," which is building up some momentum. In light of ethnographic examination into the everyday experience of India's extended time of advanced living, this article asks who must, or without a doubt can, bear the exchange expenses of this computerized ideal world. At last, the fast ascent of advanced cash has pushed these issues to the very front of social, social, and monetary examination.

R. Mohan Kumar (2019) guaranteed that current realities on the monetary effect of digitalization. By get-together and ordering research papers on India's economy will be affected by digitalization and data and correspondence advances. Everything unquestionably revolves around the computerized economy is tied in with changing the many elements of organization collaborations and exchanges, as well as permitting developments. It's not just about moving corporate exchanges from one face to another to on the web. Evaluating, Speed, Joblessness, Gross domestic product, FDI, Cash, Administration, Framework, and different factors have been recognized as basic in this.

Devapriya Chakravarty (2019) this article looks at the spread of advanced media in agricultural countries like India, breaking down the peculiarities utilizing political economy techniques. It dives into the discussion over the political economy of the computerized space and what is presently known as new media to strip back the many layers of this perplexing point. It next sees how much weight is given to computerized media's job in contending and broadcasting one's skill on a globalized stage. To all the more likely figure out the talk around India's advanced wave, the state's contribution in policymaking, possession, and starting State-supported drives is examined. Topical examination of Indian State head Narendra Modi's debut address on the send-off of Advanced India uncovers the enticing techniques used to convince the crowd to help the mission, as well as the political financial matters of Computerized Correspondence and Advanced Free enterprise in India.

Rahul Mukherjee (2018) Dependence Jio's 4G administrations, which assurance free telephone discussions and 'limitless' web streaming, have caused unrest in the Indian telecom area lately, with other cell organizations losing pay and clients. To completely comprehend this agitate in the Indian telecom industry and its effect on cell phone clients, the article contends for noticing the snare of infrastructural and stage related talks at three degrees of activity: Jio's methodologies to catch the Indian telecom market and the reactions by the main occupant different specialist co-ops to normal residents' telephone use rehearses and infrastructural experiences, and the public authority's vision for India.

Stuti Saxena (2018) the objective of this study is to underline the effect of segment factors on Indian respondents' impression of debasement. Orientation is a segment factor that impacts how individuals see debasement. Schooling, conjugal status, proficient standing, and age no affect how clients see debasement in e-taxpayer supported organizations. People in India have inborn distinctions in sexual orientation in their impression of the frequency of corruption. As an outcome, since the send-off of the "Computerized India" program, defilement in e-taxpayer supported organizations has diminished, yet ladies see the converse.

Suhasini, B (2018) as per the report, computerized advertising and correspondence are basic for laying out long haul client connections and conveying fruitful help. Client cooperation has risen quickly because of improved multi-contact point correspondence empowered by Client Relationship the executives (CRM) arrangements. CRM utilizes genuine multi-channel correspondence strategies that incorporate various long range informal communication instruments for a more extensive market reach, further developed deceivability, and expanded brand an incentive for ventures. The Public authority of India's dynamic advancement and various undertakings sent off by them have laid out a model and pattern across all corporate and social areas in India to endeavour towards the digitization of different administrations that they expect to provide for their clients in a fast and simple to-utilize way.

Karamvir Sheok (2017) the carefully instructed and enabled people can possibly change the whole economy. The robotization of monetary areas will bring about better execution and development, which will affect the economy's development rate. Cost reserve funds, expanded yield, better business, expanded efficiency, and education, among different advantages, will be acknowledged because of digitalization. Digitalization will support the improvement of all cycles in the rural and modern areas, buying, selling, stock control, exchange relations, work, and item advancement are only a couple of models. etc. On mechanization of the assistance area will add to the area's development by working with admittance to and conveyance of administrations. The interest for administrations is likewise supported by extending the client base and altering administrations to address the issues of clients. Because of more noteworthy capital and human asset use, a carefully engaged economy grows impressively rapidly, successfully, and effectively. What's more, India, as a country with such huge HR, can arrive at uncommon development rates and put the nation comparable to laid out economies if appropriately utilized.

Dr. Giridhari Mohanta and et al (2017) recognized that, Top state leader Narendra Modi sent off the computerized India drive on July 1, 2015, determined to change India into an information economy and a carefully enabled society, as well as conveying great administration for residents, fully intent on giving participatory, straightforward, and responsive government By guaranteeing that assets and administrations are accessible in local dialects and giving a helpful computerized framework to participatory administration, for example, making all administration declarations and records accessible on the Cloud with convenience, Advanced India tries to accomplish widespread advanced proficiency and admittance to all advanced assets for residents. The reason for this article is to find out about the effect of advanced India on all parts of administration and resident personal satisfaction, as well as the issues that it presents.

Ashutosh D. Gaur (2016) in the IT and BPM areas, his article investigates the meaning of 'Computerized India' in the Make in India programme. Cities are becoming savvy urban communities as the economy movements to an advanced economy, and administration is moving to e administration. It will expand the requirement for PC equipment. Computerized proficiency was underlined in the past Association spending plan as an advanced change program. The Indian government has expressed that by 2020, it plans to have no imports of IT

equipment. With the ascent of credit only exchanges, we might observe a leap in purchaser acquisition of IT equipment. This study will evaluate a few computerized change patterns and hardships.

Nagaraju LG (2016) the reason for this study is to audit the examination and show the qualities and shortcomings of India's pioneering attempts. This study depends on an intensive survey of the writing and it is generally worried about distinguishing design of hatcheries as well as government strategy as an instrument for monetary turn of events. Any nation's advancement relies upon its innovative soul and capacity to face challenges. Potential business visionaries are very important to be disregarded. They should be found, upheld, sustained, and exploited to help society in general. Their significance as monetary development specialists can't be put into words since they are the main wellsprings of new worth creation, advancement, new abundance creation, and, most urgently, new work creation. While we as a whole put stock in the proficiency of market economies and their capacity to make practical, top notch livelihoods in by far most of improvement cases, there are still pockets of advancement where markets miss the mark. Essential schooling, medical care, fundamental examination, and some applied exploration are only a couple of instances of regions where public subsidizing is required and is overall intensely used to help us develop and create.

Vinay Kumar (2016) the presentation of Person to person communication Locales (SNS) has brought about huge measures of information being created consistently. Most of these information are multimodal and unstructured, and they are developing at a remarkable rate. The expression "large information" alludes to the outstanding expansion in the assortment, sum, and intricacy of organized and unstructured information. Overseeing huge information and receiving its rewards is a significant endeavour. With more noteworthy admittance to large information vaults for different applications, security and access control are extra thought while taking care of huge information. We discussed the various utilizations of enormous information, the advantages it offers, and the hindrances we defy taking care of such immense volumes of information for assorted applications. In his review article, he likewise talks about issues connected to protection from different peril impression of huge information.

Gurpreet Kaur (2015) the connection between monetary consideration and advanced India has been expressed. Monetary consideration involves offering monetary types of assistance to the less fortunate and lower-pay sections of society with the goal that more people can profit from them. Advanced India is a drive by the Indian government to offer all occupants with taxpayer supported organizations by means of the web. The effect of the Computerized India drive on monetary consideration is examined in this exploration. The computerized India program can promptly associate many sections of society and help in the accomplishment of the objective of monetary consideration through advanced banking.

METHODOLOGY

Data: The primary data was obtained using a self-administered questionnaire, and the secondary data was acquired using a suitable sampling procedure. Historical data, periodicals, and printed materials are used to compile secondary data for the review of literature.

Research Design, Sampling plan and Sample size: The researcher collects information from 100 targeted respondents using a questionnaire for the aim of the study. For this study, male and female respondents were chosen at random from a variety of areas.

Research instruments: The acquired data was examined using statistical techniques such as percentage analysis, paired t-test, and reliability test through statistical software for mathematical reasoning in order to meet the research objectives.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

**Demographic Details of the Respondent's
Table -1**

Demographic Variables		Percentage %
GENDER	Male	65%
	Female	35%
AGE	18 - 25 Years	25%
	26 - 35 Years	15%
	36 - 45 Years	32%
	46 and Above	28%
OCCUPATION	Teachers	15%
	Personal banking manager	15%
	Common service centre	10%
	Computer Support Specialist	10%
	Common Library	10%
	Persons from public places like Railway stations, Bus Terminals, Hospitals & Malls	15%
	Government sector people (Telecommunication, Electricity, Water & Energy)	15%
Persons from Rural Sector	10%	

Demographic Details of the Respondent's

Chart -1

SOURCE: Primary data

INTERPRETATION

The table and chart-1 represents the major demographic details of the respondents like gender, age and occupation, it reveals that 65% are male respondents and 35% are female respondents. And it inferred that 25% of the respondents in the age group of 18 to 25, respondents that are 15% in the age group of 26 to 35, 32% of the respondents in the age group of 36 to 45, 28% of the respondents in the age group of 46 and above. And it shows the occupation of the respondents who impact of digital India national movement through their professions 15% of the respondents from teachers (Education sector) 15% of the respondents from personal banking manager (Banking Sector), 10%of the respondents common service centre,10%of the respondents computer Support Specialist (IT Sector),10%of the respondents common library, 15%of the persons from public places like Railway stations, Bus Terminals, Hospitals & Malls, 15%of the respondents Government sector people (Telecommunication, Electricity, Water & Energy), 10%of the persons from rural sector.

Aware of Digital India Project among the Respondents

Table -2

PARTICULAR	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
YES	70	70
NO	12	12
MAYBE	18	18
TOTAL	100	100

SOURCE: Primary data

Chart -2

Explanation

The following table and figure -2 reflect the percentage of respondents who are aware of the Digital India Programme. In Chennai, 75% of respondents are aware of the Digital India Programme, 12% have no notion, and 18% have only heard the word Digital India Programme.

Paired Samples Test

H₀: There is no relationship between Gender and 1.Digital India project will uplift the standard of living, 2. rural people can able to adopt the digital change in our country, 3. Want to live in a digitalized city and 4.Digital India project will get success.

H₁: There is a relationship between Gender and 1.Digital India project will uplift the standard of living, 2. rural people can able to adopt the digital change in our country, 3. Want to live in a digitalized city and 4.Digital India project will get success.

Table -3

Paired Samples Test									
Variables		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	DIGITAL INDIA PROJECT WILL UPLIFT THE STANDARD OF LIVING - GENDER	-.30000	.46057	.04606	-.39139	-.20861	-6.514	99	.000
Pair 2	RURAL PEOPLE CAN ABLE TO ADOPT THE DIGITAL CHANGE IN OUR COUNTRY - GENDER	.35000	.47937	.04794	.25488	.44512	7.301	99	.000
Pair 3	WANT TO LIVE IN A DIGITALIZED CITY - GENDER	.10000	.54123	.05412	-.00739	.20739	1.848	99	.068
Pair 4	DIGITAL INDIA PROJECT WILL GET SUCCESS - GENDER	.33000	.47258	.04726	.23623	.42377	6.983	99	.000

INTERPRETATION

The above table-3 inferred that the paired t-test was run on a sample of 100 to determine whether there was a statistically significant mean difference between the gender and Digital India project will uplift the standard of living (M =-30.00, SD=46.05) and the rural people can able to adopt the digital change in our country (M =35.00, SD=47.93) and want to live in a digitalized city (M =10.00, SD=54.12) and Digital India project will get success (M =33.00, SD=47.25), at the .05 level of significance. As statistically the level of significant (std. devt) of all the four variables is 46% to 55% have accepted by the respondents. Therefore as result of paired t-test the H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted.

Percentage and Reliability Statistics

Table -4

VARIABLES	LITERACY TO RURAL PEOPLE	DIGITAL EDUCATION	BOTH	ANY OTHER
THE MOST IMPORTANT THING TO CONVERT INDIA DIGITALLY	20 %	21%	54%	5%

Reliability Statistics

Table -5

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.734	2

INTERPRETATION

The above table 4 and 5 shows the percentage wise details of the respondents and their opinion about the most conversion of 20% of India's population to digital is crucial. the respondents are acknowledged that its provide literacy to rural people, 21% of the respondents are acknowledged that it's for digital education, 54% of the respondents are acknowledged the both and 5% of the respondents are acknowledged that for other purposes only the things to convert India digitally. As a result the factorial reliability and validity statistics test, Cronbach's alpha was conducted with 100 samples and the minimum value of coefficient alpha obtained was .734 this show more than 0.6 for the scale of reliable and the data has satisfactory on the most important thing to convert India digitally.

Percentage and Reliability Statistics

Table -6

VARIABLES	IT SECTOR	EDUCATIONAL SECTOR	SERVICE SECTOR	RURAL SECTOR
THE SECTOR WILL GET DEVELOPED MOST AFTER DIGITALIZATION IN NDIA	35%	18%	27%	20%

Reliability Statistics

Table -7

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.861	2

INTERPRETATION

The above table 6 and 7 shows the percentage wise details of the respondents and the opinion about the is 35 % of India is digitalized, this industry will develop the most of the respondents are accepted that IT sector has developed, 18% of the respondents are accepted that Educational sector has developed, 27% of the respondents are accepted that Service sector has developed and 20% of the respondents are accepted that Rural Sector has developed. As a result the factorial reliability and validity statistics test, Cronbach's alpha was conducted with 100 samples and the minimum value of coefficient alpha obtained was .861 this show more than

0.6 for the scale of reliable and the data has satisfactory on the sector has most developed after digitalization in India.

Percentage and Reliability Statistics

Table -8

VARIABLES	RESERVATION FACILITIES	BANKING SYSTEM	ELECTRICITY/ WATER FACILITIES	EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTE	ANY OTHER
AFTER DIGITALIZATION, THIS AREA WILL BECOME MORE CONVENIENT TO YOU AS COMPARE TO THEIR CURRENT SERVICES	15%	11%	17%	46%	11%

Reliability Statistics

Table -9

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.864	2

INTERPRETATION

The above table 8 and 9 shows the percentage wise details that is 15% of the respondents are agreed that after digitalization the reservation facilities are more convenient, 11% of the respondents are agreed that after digitalization the banking system are more convenient, 17% of the respondents are agreed that after digitalization the electricity/ water facilities are more convenient, 46%ofthe respondents are agreed that after digitalization the educational institute are more convenient, and in comparison to their existing services, 11 % of respondents believe that following digitalization, other areas will be more convenient. As a result the factorial reliability and validity statistics test, Cronbach’s alpha was conducted with 100 samples and the minimum value of coefficient alpha obtained was .864 this shows more than 0.6 for the scale of reliable and it shows that after digitalization, the above said areas will become more convenient to the respondents.

Percentage and Reliability Statistics

Table -10

VARIABLES	INTERNET CONNECTION IN EVERY RURAL AREA	DIGITALIZATION ON ALL GOVERNMENT WORK	FREE WIFI AT ALL PUBLIC PLACES	DIGITAL LITERACY	ANY OTHER
IDEA ABOUT DIGITAL INDIA	23%	20%	41%	11%	5%

Reliability Statistics

Table -11

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.834	2

INTERPRETATION

The above table 10 and 11 shows the percentage wise details and idea about digital India is 23% of the respondents are agreed that internet connection in every rural area, 20% of the respondents are agreed that digitalization on all government work, 41% of the respondents are agreed that free Wi-Fi at all public places, 11% of the respondents are agreed that digital literacy, and 5% of the respondents are agreed that the digital India is for additional purpose. As a result the factorial reliability and validity statistics test, Cronbach's alpha was conducted with 100 samples and the minimum value of coefficient alpha obtained was .834 this shows more than 0.6 for the scale of reliable and it shows that the idea about digital India of the respondents.

Percentage and Reliability Statistics

Table -12

VARIABLES	EXCELLENT	GOOD	FAIR	POOR
RATING WOULD YOU GIVE TO THIS DIGITAL INDIA PROGRAMME	24%	63%	9%	4%

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.605	2

INTERPRETATION

The above table 12 and 13 shows the percentage wise rating on Digital India Programme 24 % of the respondents are rated as Excellent, 63% of the respondents are rated as Good, 9% of the respondents are rated as Fair, and 4% of the respondents are rated as Poor. As a result the factorial reliability and validity statistics test, Cronbach's alpha was conducted with 100 samples and the minimum value of coefficient alpha obtained was .605 this shows more than 0.6 for the scale of reliable and it shows that the rating on Digital India Programme is satisfactory.

FINDINGS

A great many people today try to exist in a computerized world, and this exploration paper shows that most of individuals know about the Advanced India program and concur that digitization will work on their degree of living. During this pandemic, computerized schooling is more pivotal than any other time to change India over completely to the advanced age. Country people may have the option to adjust the progressions assuming they are given adequate computerized education and information help. Since this undertaking requires

laborers with new IT capacities, the IT area will see work possibilities. In both the help and provincial areas, there will be huge changes being developed. Instructive organizations will turn out to be more helpful because of digitization when contrasted with their ongoing administrations. As per most of individuals, the point of advanced India is to have free remote neighborhood in every public spot. Most of individuals accept. Most of individuals accept that the computerized India project is a decent one, and that it will be a tremendous achievement.

SUGGESTIONS

Advanced education is the most important move toward resident strengthening. Individuals ought to know about how to safeguard their own data while utilizing the web. To make this program a triumph, a colossal public mindfulness crusade is required. To extend web utilization, it is basic to instruct and show occupants, especially in open country and secluded areas, the benefits of approaching the web. The computerized partition should be crossed over. The public authority's solidarity isn't fabricating content. This goal requires coordinated efforts with telecom suppliers and different organizations on satisfied and benefits. For the drawn out development of computerized foundation, public-private organization (PPP) approaches should be researched. Confidential area improvement of last-mile framework in country and far off regions ought to be upheld. To help the confidential area, alluring tax collection strategies and quicker project endorsement are required.

Greatest availability with negligible network safety dangers is basic to the outcome of the advanced India project. We'll require major areas of strength for a cybercrime crew to monitor the information base and safeguard it 24 hours every day, seven days per week. To reinforce network safety abilities, we really want to fabricate graduate-level digital protection courses and urge worldwide ensuring bodies to present an assortment of expertise based network safety courses. An incredible degree of responsibility and exertion are expected, as well as compelling interest from various divisions. This objective ought to be upheld by different arrangements in numerous areas. Alterations to a few regulations that have long smothered India's innovative improvement are expected for fruitful execution.

CONCLUSION

Aside from giving admittance to schooling, wellbeing, and monetary administrations, a carefully associated India can help work on individuals' social and financial circumstances through creating non-rural monetary ventures. It is critical to feature, in any case, that ICT (Data and Correspondences Innovation) can't straightforwardly prompt the country's general turn of events. Proficiency, fundamental framework, generally speaking business environment, administrative climate, and different parts that help and upgrade by and large development and advancement can be understood. The Computerized India drive is basically the start of a computerized unrest that, if totally executed, will open up a huge number of new open doors for people.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Adrian Athique (2019), A great leap of faith: The cashless agenda in Digital India, Sage Publications, Volume: 21 issue: 8, page(s): 1697-1713, Article first published online: February 21, 2019; Issue published: August 1, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444819831324>.
2. Dr. Binod Kumar (2020), Impact of Digital India on Indian Economy, International Education & Research Journal [IERJ], E-ISSN No: 2454-9916, Volume: 6, Issue: 3, pp 12&13, March 2020.
3. Devpriya Chakravarty and Santosh Kumar Patra (2019), A Political Economic View of the Digital India Campaign, Journal of Media Studies, Vol. 34(1): January 2019, PP. 77-106, ICS Publications www.pu.edu.pk/home/journal/41
4. Dipankar Saikia , Rajeswari Das, Subhra Sahoo (2020), An Overview of the Digital India Programme with Special Reference to Agriculture, Agriculture and Food: Newsletter, ISSN No.2581-8317 Volume 2 - Issue 8 - Aug 2020, PP. 93-96, www.argifoodmagazine.co.in
5. Carla Fernandes, Maria Rosa Borges & Jorge Caiado (2021) The contribution of digital financial services to financial inclusion in Mozambique: an ARDL model approach, Applied Economics, 53:3, 400-409, DOI: 10.1080/00036846.2020.1808177.
6. Gaur, Ashutosh D., and Jasmin Padiya. "A Study Impact of 'Digital India 'in 'Make in India'Program in IT & BPM Sector." In *Fourteenth AIMS International Conference on Management*, pg, pp. 325-331. 2016.
7. Dr. Giridhari Mohanta, Dr. Sathya Swaroop Debasish, and Dr. Sudipta Kishore Nanda, A Study on Growth and Prospect of Digital India Campaign, Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies ISSN 2415-6663 (Print), ISSN 2415-6671 (Online), Vol-2, Iss-7 (Jul, 2017):727-731.
8. Gurpreet Kaur (2015), Financial Inclusion and Digital India, International Journal of Business Management, ISSN No. 2349-3402, Vol. 2(2),2015, PP.1251-1258, www.ijbm.co.in
9. Heidi Aly (2020), Digital transformation, development and productivity in developing countries: is artificial intelligence a curse or a blessing? Published in Review of Economics and Political Science, Published by Emerald Publishing Limited, e-ISSN: 2631-3561 p-ISSN: 2356-9980 DOI 10.1108/REPS-11-2019-0145, available on Emerald Insight at: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/2631-3561.htm>.
10. Karamvir Sheok and Neha Gupta (2017), Digital India programme and impact of digitalization on Indian economy, Indian Journal of Economics and Development, Vol 5 (5), May 2017 I, ISSN (online): 2320-9836 ISSN (Print):2320-9828, pp 1-13.
11. R. Mohan Kumar (2019), Impact of Digitalization on Economy in India: Review of Literature, International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology, Volume 4, Issue 5, May – 2019, pp 8-10, ISSN No:- 2456-2165, IJISRT19MY57, www.ijisrt.com
12. Nagaraju L G (2016), Digitization of Indian Agriculture , Presidency Journal of Management Thought & Research, Number 3, Page Number 25- 33, Vol. IX, No.1, January – June 2019, ISSN 2229-5275
13. Dr Pardeep Bawa Sharm and Dr Roktim Sarmah(2020), Perception And Awareness of Youth Towards Digital India Campaign, International Journal of Management (IJM) Volume 11, Issue 6, June 2020, pp. 1381-1393, Article ID: IJM_11_06_127, ISSN Print: 0976-6502 and ISSN Online: 0976-6510 DOI: 10.34218/IJM.11.6.2020.127
14. Rajan Gupta (2020) Regional E-governance Development Index for Developing Nations, Digital Government: Research and Practice, Volume 1, Issue 3 November 2020 Article No.: 20pp 1–26 <https://doi.org/10.1145/3386163>.

15. Rahul Mukherjee (2018), Jio sparks Disruption 2.0: infrastructural imaginaries and platform ecosystems in 'Digital India', Sage publications, Volume: 41 issue: 2, page(s): 175-195, Article first published online: December 21, 2018; Issue published: March 1, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443718818383>.
16. Saxena, S. (2018), "Perception of corruption in e-government services post-launch of "Digital India": role of demographic variables", Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance, Emerald Publishing Limited, Vol. 20 No. 2, pp. 163-177. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DPRG-02-2017-0007>.
17. Shruti Jain (2020), The Rising Fourth Wave: Feminist Activism on Digital Platforms in India, July 2020, Observer Research Foundation (ORF), Issue No. 384, pp 1-15, ISBN: 978-93-90159-47-5.
18. Subhadeep Dutta (2020), Digital Education Plays A Role Of Library: A Comparative Study In Digital Era. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical & Applied Sciences, 1(1), 34-41. Retrieved from <http://cajotas.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJOTAS/article/view/23>.
19. Suhasini. B, and N Santhosh Kumar (2018) Digital India – Transforming Customer Relationship Management in Higher Education, Journal of Applied Management - Jidnyasa; Pune Vol. 10, Iss. 1, (Jan-Jun 2018): PP. 51-59.
20. Vinay Kumar, Arpana Chaturvedi and Poonam Verma (2016), Applications of Big Data in the Digital India: Opportunities and Challenges, RA-International Journal of Technology & Engineering ISSN 2455-4480; Vol.03, Issue 03 (2016) Institute of Research Advances <http://research-advances.org/index.php/IRAJTE>